

On Darwin and Computation

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It looks like Las Vegas is roaring again in 2023. It almost feels like forever riding this boom and bust cycle since moving here in 2009 when everything was on a seemingly hopeless downslope, then up, and down again. Now, the highways are expanding, the Raiders have finally moved into their new stadium, Formula 1 is coming as well with a brand new Las Vegas Grand Prix four-mile track right on the strip, and public art in the entire southern region is thriving. Isn't that what cities are supposed to do anyway, capitalism shimmying its way to progress?

Something feels different though, as if the attitude of the city in its entirety is radically changing. Las Vegas will always be the casino capital it has always been, but pockets of other industries augmenting this enterprise (for instance, the film and fashion industry, and other cultural and entertainment venues such as the Smith's Center and Meow Wolf in Area 15) are all maturing a lot faster in the last decade. Is it because the Internet has given us a better way to steer and take stock of our evolving culture?

Modern technology has definitely played a big role in shaping contemporary "high culture" as that great equalizer of "virtue" — a fusion experiment converging everyone's opinions into a giant head-on collision inside that virtual Tokamak we call Social Media. Things have gone way far beyond anything we could have ever imagined when the first bootleg of Windows came out in the 1990s. All this cultural exchange now happens in real-time blitzkrieg speeds wherein every single bit counts. We've barely been given ample time at all for a pause to contemplate our situatedness in the world, and in a split second it's gone — all that remains in the aftermath is an average split, a clean yes or no, blue or red, friend or foe in a black and white kind of a stalemate monoculture. How does painting exist at all with the nuances of grays all washed out in this fast-paced 007 kind of world? Is this new pace for the new generation of artists a good thing or a bad thing, who knows? Maybe we'll adapt, maybe we'll settle, we'll see.

Speaking of social media, in one of those heated debates on Facebook, I remember the late Dave Hickey saying that Las Vegas was the perfect city for artists to live and work. But he added that the art that we do here, at some point, must come to terms with the strip and its ominous presence and imposing beauty, as well as its rich history that lies beneath the rubble from decades of architectural and cultural implosions. Yet somewhere in the middle of all that, he also insisted that we have managed to marginalize and neglect beauty and have instead celebrated the institutionalization of mediocrity — that art has merely

become a useful sociopolitical propaganda tool to advance ideologies and critical movements. Tempting, isn't it? But isn't the strip itself the epitome of aesthetic mediocrity as well? It's interesting how worldviews can get so convoluted so easily: to consider, from an artist's perspective, what Hickey says what artists "must" do, from a critic's point of view. See what that did there? Perhaps it's really not that important what critics say, but what it does, how it pokes what's inside of us, to help us look deeply into the essence of what we're really doing here.

If we see the art world as a hyperobject — agents, objects, dealers, artifacts and everything else you can throw in there — an aggregate of stuff so large that it's impossible to rationalize the entropy that ensues as we each go about our own business, then it doesn't make sense at all to question who needs what and what needs whom. If culture is some kind of perpetually self-correcting "working memory" that processes the complexity of interrelationships in the world, then maybe everyone's got a role, or no role at all, maybe everyone gets to pitch-in and stir this melting pot of a culture, and whatever works, just works, the rest just burns out to help fuel the flames of proclivity.

I forget that painting is a kind of technology as well, though sometimes it may appear more rudimentary/primitive than it really is — hacking and slashing, squishing and scraping, manipulating the paint until you've almost accidentally come across what you're looking for. What might seem like randomness and chance could very well be an elaborate system of spontaneous creativity, wherein "emergence" plays an essential role in reaching beyond "purpose" and "intention".

Painter Manuel Ocampo says the problem with some artists is that "they cannot escape language... they hold on to it tightly the more they try to let go of it". How else is one to express that which is unknown (to language) in the same way that poetry and philosophy does, groping its way into the darkest of depths, reaching for what is ultimately forever withdrawn from the limits of human cognition? One thing's for sure, that the ingenuity and beauty in the artifacts we've created throughout human history must be undeniable proof that a much more complex system of "mapping-out" relationships between irreducible ideas exists behind the simplicity of mark-making.

A couple of years back, I was fortunate enough to have been invited by painter Phil King, to teach/mentor in one of the most innovative painting schools in London: Turps Art School, spearheaded by YBA artist Marcus Harvey. One of the things I've stressed in their Correspondence Course is that perhaps we ought to think less and do more, and allow our unconscious to just do its thing. In the program, there's a kind of clarity that's achieved in discourse from casual

conversation about painting, in keeping the “process” open enough that it preserves the irreducible nature of aesthetics from which wisdom emerges, as opposed to traditional instruction. In spite of all our intentions, real progress in painting just happens on its own, you can only steer so much of it until you realize there’s no choice but to allow the “imagery” to unfold on its own terms.

In the Journal of Researches, Charles Darwin states: “It is not possible for the mind to comprehend, except by a slow process, any effect which is produced by a cause repeated so often that the multiplier itself conveys an idea not more definite than the savage implies when he points to the hairs of his head.” Thinking about painting in this way reminds me of the algorithmic beauty of cellular automata, and the unprecedented level of complexity that somehow emerges from the very simplest of means. In fact, in one of these systems called Rule 30, physicist Stephen Wolfram believes that the distinct forms that emerge from simple repeating rules on a grid are the keys to understanding how the very same complex structures and behaviors emerge in nature.

Is painting just a thing that we do? A remnant of evolutionary biology, like the bark of a dog, or the chirping of birds? It’s always tempting to rationalize intention into all of these things, like assuming “love” as merely a tool to procreate and propagate, to ensure the evolutionary continuity of a species. Beyond instruction, beyond the intentions of artists, beyond the annals of art history, beyond the honoraries of prestigious institutions and galleries, beyond the rambling whataboutisms of critics with the likes of Saltz’s or Smith’s of the world, what is it that we’re really trying to convey here in painting, if we’re even conveying anything at all?

For all we know, maybe that’s how we ought to “come to terms” with the strip and its eternally evolving form — from a railway stopover, to a casino highway, into an F1 racetrack. It’s all the same as art and painting, we accept the changing pace of our evolving contemporary culture that happens right before our very eyes. We adapt, we settle, we procreate and propagate the evolution of our species, whatever it takes to get us to play out whatever or whenever its finality is.